

EXP: Modeling Perceptual Fluency with Visual Representations in an Intelligent Tutoring System for Undergraduate Chemistry

1 Vision and Goals

Visual representations are ubiquitous instructional tools in science, technology, engineering, and math (STEM) domains (Ainsworth, 2008; NRC, 2006). For example, instructors use the visual representations shown in Figure 1 to help students learn chemical bonding. Yet, to a novice student, these visual representations may not be

Figure 1. Representations of water. **a:** Lewis structure; **b:** ball-and-stick figure; **c:** space-filling model; **d:** electrostatic potential map (EPM)

helpful because the student may not know how to interpret the representations. For example, does the red color in the ball-and-stick figure (Figure 1-b) mean the same thing as in the electrostatic potential map (EPM; Figure 1-d)? (It does not.) Instructors often ask students to use visual representations that they have never seen before to make sense of concepts that they have not yet learned about (Airey & Linder, 2009; Wertsch & Kazak, 2011), an issue known as the *representation dilemma* (Dreher & Kuntze, 2014). Hence, to succeed in STEM, students need *representation skills* that enable them to use visual representations to make sense of and solve domain-relevant problems (Ainsworth, 2006; Gilbert, 2005).

Crucial representation skills involve students' ability to make connections among visual representations (Ainsworth, 2006; Schnotz, 2005). For example, students need to understand each representation in Figure 1 shows complementary conceptual aspects about chemical bonding. To do so, the student maps the lone electrons shown as dots in the Lewis structure (Figure 1-a) to the EPM's red region (Figure 1-d), which shows that the lone electrons result in high electron density.

Educational technologies are particularly suitable to support representation skills because they can provide adaptive support while students solve domain-relevant problems (Koedinger & Corbett, 2006; VanLehn, 2011). To do so, these technologies use a cognitive model that infers whether the student has learned target skills based on her/his interactions with the technology. Research shows that adapting instruction to students' representation skills can enhance those skills (Tuckey, Selvaratnam, & Bradley, 1991) and learning of domain knowledge (Davidowitz & Chittleborough, 2009).

However, educational technologies for representation skills have two critical limitations. First, they typically focus on one type of representation skill: students' conceptual understanding of representations (e.g., the ability to explain correspondences among visual features across representations). This focus mimics education psychology research's focus on conceptual learning (Ainsworth, 2006; Seufert, 2003). However, research suggests a second type of representation skill is crucial for students' learning success: *perceptual fluency* (Kellman & Massey, 2013; Massey, Kellman, Roth, & Burke, 2011), the ability to rapidly and effortlessly translate among representations. This ability results from *implicit forms of learning*. For example, expert chemists simply "see" that the representations in Fig. 1 show the same molecule.

Second, of the few educational technologies that enhance perceptual fluency, their adaptive capabilities are limited and their perceptual supports rely solely on performance measures (e.g., accuracy, response times) to adapt to students' representation skills (Kellman, Massey, & Son, 2009; Massey et al., 2011). They do not use a cognitive model of the latent skills that students acquire through perceptual learning. As a result, they cannot provide specific feedback when students make mistakes. We must overcome this limitation because decades of research show cognitive models can dramatically increase the effectiveness of educational technologies (Anderson, Boyle, Corbett, & Lewis, 1990; VanLehn, 2011).

These limitations likely result from cognitive modeling's traditional focus on explicit, verbally accessible knowledge. To develop cognitive models, researchers analyze how students think about target skills (Koedinger & Corbett, 2006; Rau, Aleven, Rummel, & Rohrbach, 2013). We typically ask students to verbalize their problem-solving steps (Clark, Feldon, Van Merriënboër, Yates, & Early, 2007; Schraagen, Chipman, & Shalin, 2000). Yet, verbalization is not suitable for assessing perceptual learning processes, which are implicit and not verbally accessible (Kellman & Massey, 2013; Koedinger, Corbett, & Perfetti,

2012). Thus, to create perceptual supports that take advantage of adaptive capabilities that enhance conceptual learning, we need to develop cognitive models for perceptual learning. These new technology and socio-technical models will help learners develop interests in STEM fields, deepen their understanding of complicated concepts and phenomena, and foster their learning of complex practices and skills. In addition, we will expand our understanding of how new adaptive technologies can influence learning.

The goal of this project is to develop a new methodology for cognitive modeling of perceptual learning processes so as to create adaptive technologies that support perceptual fluency. The proposed project will advance our understanding of how best to foster implicit learning through adaptive technologies. We will develop and evaluate this methodology through experiments conducted in the context of undergraduate chemistry (i.e., using the visual representations in Figure 1). Each experiment will be analyzed with machine learning methods that will yield a cognitive model for adaptive perceptual support. A final experiment will evaluate whether integrating adaptive perceptual support with conceptual instruction enhances chemistry learning. To achieve this goal, we will take these four steps:

First, we will use *metric learning* to assess which visual features novice students and chemistry experts focus on when presented with visual representations. Comparing novice to expert perceptions will establish which visual features perceptual support should help students attend to (e.g., because experts focus on them but novices do not). Hence, metric learning will provide a skill model of student perceptions (i.e., analogous to what verbalization techniques provide in traditional cognitive modeling).

Second, we will use *machine learning* methods to develop a cognitive model of perceptual learning. The typical setup in machine learning is that a cognitive model (i.e., an algorithm) learns from a set of examples to achieve a desired learning outcome. In our case, the example set corresponds to perceptual learning tasks presented to students as part of the intervention. The desired learning outcome will be determined based on the metric approach. We will test several cognitive models, drawing on our prior research on cognitive modeling of representation skills (Rau, Aleven, Rummel, & Pardos, 2014). We will test whether the cognitive model should include student characteristics. For example, spatial ability affects students' learning success in STEM (Rau, 2015b; Stieff, 2013).

Third, we will use *machine teaching* to optimize the example sets for students. Machine teaching, a method co-principal investigator (PI) Zhu (2015) developed, uses machine learning to reverse-engineer ideal example sets. Given the desired learning outcome (obtained from metric learning) and cognitive model (obtained from machine learning), we will construct the ideal example set as a selection and sequence of representations. We define *ideal* in terms of student efficiency in achieving learning outcomes.

Fourth, we will use the adaptive educational technology *Chem Tutor* for undergraduate chemistry (Rau, 2015a; Rau, Michaelis, & Fay, 2015) to implement our approach. Chem Tutor includes conceptual support for representation skills and a preliminary non-adaptive version of perceptual support. An in vivo experiment will evaluate effectiveness of the new adaptive perceptual support.

2 The Innovation

This proposal combines educational psychology, cognitive science, and machine learning to establish a next-generation methodology for cognitive modeling of perceptual fluency. The cognitive model will serve as a basis for adaptive perceptual support to help students acquire representation skills that are crucial to success in chemistry. Given that visual representations play a similar role in other STEM domains, our methodological approach and research findings will likely generalize to a large number of domains. This project will address educational technologies' current inability to adequately adapt instruction to individual students' perceptual fluency. At the same time, this project will yield novel algorithms for similarity judgments that will allow us to more efficiently collect judgment data from human subjects. Further, the project will serve as an evaluation of the machine teaching method to reverse-engineer optimal learning task sequences based on machine learning methods. Finally, the results from the proposed research will be integrated into an existing adaptive educational technology for undergraduate chemistry learning (see screen shots in supplementary materials) that we will disseminate to instructors of diverse student populations, including students at 2- and 4-year colleges and universities. We will disseminate our findings to the research communities on educational psychology, cognitive science, and machine learning.

3 Related Research

3.1 Importance of Representation Skills for Success in STEM

Visual representations play a prominent role in STEM instruction because many key concepts are abstract in nature or cannot be observed with the regular eye (Gilbert, 2005; Uttal & O'Doherty, 2008). Because different representations emphasize different conceptual aspects of the to-be-learned content, STEM instruction typically uses *multiple* visual representations. To integrate the different conceptual aspects into a coherent mental model of the domain knowledge, students need to learn an important representation skill: the ability to make connections among the representations (Ainsworth, 2006; Schnotz, 2005). However, connection-making is a difficult representation skill that many students fail to acquire (de Jong et al., 1998; McElhaney, Chang, Chiu, & Linn, 2015). Students' difficulties in making connections jeopardize their learning success in STEM domains (Ainsworth, 2008; Cheng & Gilbert, 2009). Students with low spatial ability have particular difficulties in making such connections (Stieff, 2007).

Two lines of research explore how students acquire representation skills. The first focuses on *conceptual understanding*: the ability to map features of representations to domain-relevant concepts (Ainsworth, 2006; Schnotz, 2005). Cognitive psychology suggests students learn to make such mappings through conceptual sense-making (Koedinger et al., 2012), verbally mediated, explanation-based processes used to reason about principles (Chi, Bassok, Lewis, Reimann, & Glaser, 1989; Gentner, 1983).

A second line of research suggests *perceptual fluency* is an important representation skill (Gibson, 2000; Kellman & Massey, 2013). Students with perceptual fluency can rapidly and effortlessly translate between visual representations by relying on visual features such as color, geometry, and shape. Perceptual fluency is an important aspect of expertise because it frees "cognitive head room" to engage in higher-order conceptual thinking about domain-relevant concepts (Goldstone & Barsalou, 1998; Richman, Gobet, Staszewski, & Simon, 1996). Cognitive psychology suggests perceptual fluency results from inductive, implicit processes that students engage in when learning to discriminate and categorize efficiently (Koedinger et al., 2012; Richman et al., 1996). Perceptual learning processes are often non-verbal and not necessarily willful or planned (Kellman & Massey, 2013; Koedinger et al., 2012).

3.2 Representation Skills in Chemistry

Chemistry is a prime example of a domain that heavily relies on visual representations (De Jong & Taber, 2014; Taber, 2009) because many phenomena cannot be observed with the regular eye (Taber, 2013) and are inherently visuo-spatial (Hinze et al., 2013; Wu & Shah, 2004). Chemists use visual representations to think, solve problems, and communicate (Kozma, Chin, Russell, & Marx, 2000; Schönborn & Anderson, 2006). Hence, representation skills are key to chemistry learning (Justi, Gilbert, & Ferreira, 2009; Wu, Krajcik, & Soloway, 2001). As in other STEM domains, chemistry students struggle with visual representations (Johnstone, 1991; Taber, 2013). Students' frequent failure to acquire representation skills jeopardizes their learning success in chemistry (Dori & Barak, 2001; Talanquer, 2013). Even Ph.D. students lack crucial representation skills (Strickland, Kraft, & Bhattacharyya, 2010). Hence, supporting representation skills is a major goal in chemistry education (Cheng & Gilbert, 2009; Talanquer, 2013).

Like educational psychology research, research in chemistry education has focused on conceptual understanding of visual representations (Kozma & Russell, 2005a; Stieff, 2005). Conceptual support for representation skills helps students to engage in explicit, verbally mediated reasoning about how representations show complementary or corresponding information about concepts.

However, chemistry expertise also involves *perceptual fluency in translating* among representations (Kozma & Russell, 2005b; Kozma & Russell, 1997). For example, Airey and Lindner (2009) argue perceptual fluency is achieved when translation of representations becomes "unproblematic, almost second nature" (p. 10). Chemistry education literature shows that students' lack of perceptual fluency results in their failure to "see" concepts visual representations depict (Airey & Linder, 2009; Talanquer, 2013), which interferes with learning about chemistry (Gilbert, 2005; Taber, 2014). For example, perceptual fluency may enable students to follow a complex explanation of chemical bonding because students do not have to invest cognitive effort into translating across the visual representations. Students with low spatial ability may find it difficult to acquire representation skills. In many STEM domains, (Uttal et al., 2013;

Wai, Lubinski, & Benbow, 2009), including chemistry (Stieff, 2007, 2013), students with low spatial ability show lower achievement and are less likely to pursue careers in these domains. Therefore, an important goal in STEM education is to help students with low spatial ability acquire representation skills.

3.3 Adaptive Educational Technologies

Adaptive educational technologies provide a productive venue for our research for the following reasons. First, educational technologies play an increasingly important role in education (Eichler & Peeples, 2013). For example, thanks to the availability of course management systems such as Moodle and increasing enrollments in face of decreasing financial resources, schools and universities are increasingly relying on educational technologies. Creating more effective educational technologies is therefore appropriate and timely. Second, supports for representation skills can be integrated into almost any type of educational technology in which students use visual representations to solve domain-relevant problems. A push toward such technologies that support learning with interactive visual representations results from recommendations of discipline-based research and practice guides to engage students in hands-on activities (Bodner & Domin, 2000; NRC, 2006). Thus, our focus on educational technologies is synergistic with current trends in educational technology. Third, conducting research with educational technologies allows us to collect fine-grained data about how students' learning processes unfold over time. We can use these data to better understand psychological questions about students' learning, and as a basis for refining and improving technologies. Hence, technologies can serve as the connective tissue between theory and practice. Finally, the most important advantage of focusing on educational technologies results from their capability to adapt to the individual student's needs in real time, which has been shown to contribute to their effectiveness for STEM learning (VanLehn, 2011).

One successful type of adaptive educational technologies are *intelligent tutoring systems* (ITSs). Grounded in cognitive theories of learning and artificial intelligence, they pose complex problem-solving activities and provide individualized step-by-step guidance at any point during the problem-solving process (VanLehn, 2011). At the heart of ITSs lies a cognitive model that maps students' problem-solving steps to the skills for which the ITS provides practice. This model can detect multiple strategies a student might use to solve a problem. Based on the cognitive model, ITSs provide detailed feedback and hints on how to solve the next step, thereby scaffolding skill acquisition (Corbett, Koedinger, & Hadley, 2001). In addition, ITSs can trace the student's acquisition of specific skills over time and select appropriate problems so the student receives practice opportunities on yet-to-be mastered skills that are within the student's reach. At a technical level, cognitive models that yield the adaptive capabilities of ITSs infer whether the student has learned the given skill using *latent knowledge estimation* models (Baker & Siemens, 2014). These machine-learning models estimate the likelihood of the student's knowledge level based on (1) a model of what constitutes a given skill, (2) all past student interactions related to that skill, and (3) individual student parameters (e.g., spatial skills). However, existing educational technologies for representation skills fall short of leveraging the adaptive capabilities that cognitive models offer.

3.3.1 Educational Technologies with Perceptual Fluency Support

A survey of the landscape of educational technologies that focus on representation skills makes clear the technologies mimic the gap in psychology and chemistry education. While most technologies support conceptual understanding of representations, only a few support perceptual fluency. To the best of our knowledge, no educational technology combine support for conceptual understanding and perceptual fluency—apart from the Chem Tutor ITS that PI Rau developed (detailed below).

Kellman, a member of our advisory board, spearheaded development of perceptual fluency supports. He and colleagues developed technologies with perceptual fluency support in math, chemistry, medicine, and geography. Perceptual fluency support provides students with many examples of visual representations while asking them to rapidly classify representations. Students engage in these tasks over many short trials while receiving correctness feedback. For example, a student is asked to select one of several ball-and-stick models that show the same chemical molecule as a given Lewis structure. These trials expose students to systematic variation, often in the form of contrasting cases, so irrelevant features vary but relevant features remain constant across several trials. Kellman and colleagues established the effective-

ness of perceptual fluency support in a number of controlled experiments and observational studies in several domains, including algebra, fractions, and chemistry (Kellman & Massey, 2013). Results show learning gain in perceptual fluency that transfer to novel examples and gains in domain knowledge.

However, these perceptual fluency supports do not take full advantage of adaptive capabilities that have been proven successful for explicit forms of learning. Kellman and colleagues' perceptual supports are adaptive in that they track students' accuracy and response speed. Until students achieve a mastery threshold defined (i.e., accurate responses provided with sufficient speed), they receive the same examples again and again—each example is considered a skill in its own right. In other words, existing perceptual supports lack a cognitive model that maps each problem to smaller set of latent skills students have to learn. In perceptual learning, these latent skills correspond to mappings between visual features that, once learned, students can apply to a variety of problems using these features. Hence, without a cognitive model, existing perceptual supports may not adequately describe students' perceptual learning processes and hence may not adequately select the most appropriate example problems to practice perceptual fluency.

A second limitation that results from the lack of a cognitive model is that current perceptual supports do not provide specific feedback when students make mistakes. Instead, students receive only correctness feedback: that is, they are told that their response was wrong and are given the correct answer. A cognitive model would enable educational technologies to provide feedback on the perceptual feature the student failed to pay attention to. This type of feedback may help students learn more quickly and accurately which visual features provide important cues for mappings. Expanding the adaptiveness of feedback in perceptual supports may significantly enhance their effectiveness and efficiency.

3.3.2 *Educational Technologies for Chemistry Learning*

Despite the importance of representation skills for chemistry learning, most commercially available educational technologies do not explicitly focus on representation skills. The PI informally reviewed homework systems that are commonly used at the college level (e.g., Cengage Learning's OWLv2 (www.cengage.com), ALEKS (www.aleks.com), Pearson's Mastering Chemistry and MyLab (www.pearsonmylabandmastering.com), Norton's SmartWork (smartwork.wwnorton.com), and Sapling's General Chemistry (www2.saplinglearning.com/general-chemistry). These products lack exercises that focus on perceptual aspects of representation skills, and they do not adapt to representation skills.

The few educational technologies that do support representation skills mostly focus on conceptual understanding of representations. For example, Connected Chemistry (Stieff, 2005) presents students with multiple representations of phase changes; the system allows students to manipulate one representation while observing changes in another. SVM:Chem (Kozma & Russell, 2005a) facilitates class discussions and homework questions by exposing students to graphical and symbolic representations. ChemSense (Michalchik, Rosenquist, Kozma, Kreikemeier, & Schank, 2008) presents a variety of representations and enhances collaborative learning. eChem (Wu et al., 2001) helps students make connections among representations by providing feedback and hints. Several tools visualize electrostatic functions (Chung, 2013; Csizmar et al., 2013) and molecular structure (Glasser, Herraes, & Hanson, 2009; Hanson, 2010), but they support exploration rather than scaffolded problem solving.

Only a few recent interventions focus on *perceptual fluency*, but these are not technology-based. Eastwood (2013) describes a case study of a game that helps students become fluent in translating from symbolic representations to physical ball-and-stick figures. Moreira (2013) describes an observational study of students learning to rapidly name molecules. Both studies show positive effects on engagement and reproduction, but neither assessed learning outcomes. Several online games support perceptual fluency. For instance, in Spectral Game (Bradley, Lancashire, Lang, & Williams, 2009), students translate among representations. However, the game does not include instruction on chemistry concepts.

In summary, the current state of educational technologies in chemistry reflects the previously mentioned trend in research to perceptual fluency. As a result, educational technologies are missing an important opportunity to help students acquire not only conceptual understanding but also perceptual fluency with visual representations, which will enhance their success in chemistry. By establishing a principled methodology for adaptive perceptual support will likely yield more effective instruction not only for chemistry but other STEM domains and will enhance learning outcomes in these domains.

3.4 Metric Learning to Assess Perceptions

When creating perceptual fluency support, instructional designers typically make “educated guesses” as to which visual features novice students may pay attention to. These educated guesses are based on the novice-expert literature, which documents the fact that novices tend to rely on surface features; i.e., easily perceivable visual cues such as color and shape, to judge the similarity between stimuli items. Metric learning is a machine learning method that provides a formal approach to investigating how people perceive similarity and hence provides a way of evaluating “educated guesses” that typically provide the foundation for the development of perceptual fluency support.

At a technical level, the aim of metric learning is to represent a set of items (e.g., molecules) in d -dimensional Euclidean space so the distances agree with perceptually judged dissimilarities between the items. This problem is tackled as follows. We hypothesize perceptual dissimilarities between n items can be characterized by points x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n in d -dimensional Euclidean space; i.e., the distances between the points correspond to perceptual dissimilarity. The locations of the points are unknown to us, but we can learn about the locations by asking human subjects comparative questions of the form “Is item x_k is closer to x_i than x_j ?” for any distinct i, j, k in the set $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$. We will refer to such questions as *triplet comparisons*. The goal is to identify an embedding d -dimensional space consistent with such comparative judgments. This classic problem is addressed with non-metric multi-dimensional scaling (Borg & Groenen, 2005), a technique that provides researchers with a graphical or spatial representation of the human-perceived relationships among items. For example, researchers have used embeddings to explain voting behavior and ideological relationships among candidates for office (Gormley & Murphy, 2007) and to understand how sonar experts perceive similarities among sonar returns (Philips, Pitton, & Atlas, 2006).

People are better at providing ordinal (comparative) responses than at providing fine-grained quantitative judgments or ratings (Stewart et al., 2005). For example, when asked to compare the visual representations in Figure 1, people find it easier to judge whether the Lewis structure (Figure 1-a) or the ball-and-stick model (Figure 1-b) is more similar to the space-filling model (Figure 1-c), than to judge their similarity on a rating scale. However, machine-learning perceptual embeddings from comparisons is challenging due to the sheer number of possible triplet comparisons that could be made; the number of distinct triplets is proportional to n^3 . For example, with $n=100$ items there exist nearly 500,000 distinct triplets. Researchers have observed that while triplet comparisons are easy to answer, they can become tedious and boring after extended sessions (Bijmolt & Wedel, 1995). Since we hypothesize the perceptual dissimilarities can be accurately represented in d -dimensional space, it is reasonable to conjecture that if the embedding dimension is low, i.e., $d \ll n$, then there will be a high degree of redundancy among the triplet comparisons. In fact, researchers have observed that a small subset of these triplet comparisons often suffice to learn a reasonably accurate embedding, lending support to this conjecture (Agarwal et al., 2007; Johnson, 1973; Tamuz, Liu, Belongie, Shamir, & Kalai, 2011).

Co-PI Nowak proved that roughly $(dn \log n)$ triplet comparisons are required to learn a perceptual embedding, far fewer than the total number. Furthermore, he proposed algorithms that learn good embeddings from $(dn \log n)$ carefully selected triplet comparisons (Jamieson & Nowak, 2011). If $n=100$ items and $d=2$, then $dn \log n$ about 1000, whereas the total number of triplets is about 500,000. Hence, this algorithm can significantly reduce the number of comparative judgments needed to learn perceptual embeddings. This approach thus allows for more efficient ways of assessing human perceptions of similarity among visual stimuli. At a practical level, this approach will allow us to create shorter surveys that assess peoples’ perceptions of chemical molecules and other visual stimuli. This research will address the following unsolved issues and questions on learning perceptual embeddings from comparative judgments:

1. Experimentally, embeddings learned from comparative judgments can predict outcomes of new human judgments. That is, if item x_k is closer to x_i than x_j in the learned embedding, then we predict that humans will make the same judgment. This prediction is often correct. Yet, there is no mathematical quantification of this observation. *Intuition suggests that collecting more comparative judgments will lead to more accurate embeddings and predictions, but the precise relationship is not understood.*

- Algorithms used to compute embeddings from comparative judgments are not well understood. Currently, no existing algorithm is guaranteed to find the correct embedding, *even when the comparative judgments are synthetically generated to perfectly agree with a certain embedding*.
- Often, people know about items' additional characteristics (e.g., color or shape). Such features may play a key role in perceptual judgments, but existing embedding algorithms ignore them.

Applying metric learning to the case of perceptual fluency in chemistry learning will allow us to overcome these limitations while helping us understand how students acquire perceptual fluency.

3.5 Machine Teaching

Machine teaching is an inverse problem of machine learning (Zhu, 2015). Given a cognitive model (i.e., a learning algorithm and a target model), machine teaching seeks the shortest sequence of learning tasks (i.e., the smallest training set D) such that when given D , the learning algorithm learns the target model. Machine teaching can be viewed as a communication problem between a teacher and the student: The goal is to communicate the target model using the shortest message; the channel only allows messages in the form of a training set; and the decoder is the student who decodes with the learning algorithm. In perceptual learning, the student learns visual features to fluently translate between visual representations.

In the context of education, the learning algorithm is the computational cognitive model A of a human student (e.g., an artificial neural network). The teacher wants to teach the student a target model θ^* , which corresponds to the educational goal and is known to the teacher. θ^* can be replaced with a test set, then the teacher's goal is for the student to learn a model with the smallest test set error. The teacher knows the student's learning algorithm A and teaches by giving the student a training set $D=(x_1,y_1) \dots (x_n,y_n)$ with labeled items x_i and y_i . Machine teaching aims to design the optimal (e.g., smallest or least costly) training set D . Figure 2 illustrates machine teaching. The cognitive model A maps training set D to model θ . The inverse function $A^{-1}\theta^*$ returns the set of training sets that can teach the learning algorithm θ^* . Among them, the teacher aims to identify the optimal (e.g., the smallest) training set.

Machine teaching is an optimization problem: $\min_D \text{TeachingLoss}(A(D), \theta^*) + \lambda \text{TeachingEffort}(D)$ (Zhu, 2015). That is, the teacher aims to find an optimal training set D such that the student learns a model close to the target model θ^* with the least teaching effort. The teaching loss function measures how well-taught the learning algorithm is, e.g., by the test set error of $A(D)$. The teaching effort function measures the effort the teacher must spend to teach the student, for example the size of D . λ here is a weight balancing the two. In general, this is a bilevel optimization problem. Preliminary work (Zhu, 2015; Mei & Zhu, 2015) has identified efficient solutions.

Machine teaching provides a unique approach to enhance education and personnel training. In principle, we can use machine teaching to design the optimal lesson for learning from examples that match the needs of individual students. Machine teaching complements existing approaches to designing ITSs and other educational technologies. Because implicit learning—including perceptual learning—involves learning from examples, applying machine teaching to the visual representations used in undergraduate chemistry will allow us to establish the optimal selection and sequence of perceptual tasks. This approach will make a novel contribution to the field of machine learning because, to date, the machine teaching approach has not yet been applied to realistic visual stimuli that vary on more than two dimensions.

4 Prior Work

4.1 Chem Tutor: An Intelligent Tutoring System for Undergraduate Chemistry

To address shortcomings in educational technologies in chemistry, PI Rau developed an ITS for undergraduate chemistry learning that focuses on conceptual and perceptual representation skills. The design of Chem Tutor followed a learner-centered approach, which involved surveys of undergraduate chemistry students, interviews and eye-tracking studies with undergraduate and graduate students, and extensive pilot testing (Rau, under review; Rau et al., 2015). Chem Tutor has several units that cover different chemistry topics and features interactive tools students can use to construct representations. Chem

Figure 2. Logic underlying machine teaching.

Tutor includes functionalities common to ITSs: hints for current problem-solving steps and error-specific feedback. Chem Tutor features conceptual support for representation skills. In conceptual problems, students receive prompts to explain mappings across representations, and they use interactive representation tools to construct one visual representation given another representation. The perceptual support problems were designed based on Kellman and colleagues' perceptual learning paradigm: Students encounter numerous short classification problems and receive immediate correctness feedback on these problems (red for incorrect, green for correct). Problems vary irrelevant visual features of the representations and contrast features that provide relevant information. To encourage students to rely on non-verbal, perceptual strategies while solving these problems, Chem Tutor shows a prompt before each problem asking students to "solve this problem fast, without overthinking it." Figure 3 shows an example of two perceptual problems in which students translate between Lewis structure and EPMs based on perceptual features such as electron dots and geometry. Additional screen shots are provided in supplementary materials.

Perceptual Numerous, short classification tasks Contrasting cases for visual features Correctness feedback only	Bonding Here is a Lewis structure.	
	Which EPM shows the SAME molecule? Solve this task fast and intuitively, without overthinking it.	Which EPM shows the SAME molecule? Solve this task fast and intuitively, without overthinking it.

Figure 3. Perceptual fluency support in Chem Tutor: Students have to attend to perceptual features to solve these problems, for instance to the lone pairs (left) or to the molecule's geometry (right).

Chem Tutor was tested in studies in the lab and as online homework in an introductory-level chemistry course (Rau, 2015a). These studies showed significant learning gains with large effect sizes between $d = 1.02$ and $d = 1.32$. The prototypes are available online for free, and users can try them out without signing up (<https://chem.tutorshop.web.cmu.edu/>).

4.2 Metric Learning to Assess Student Perceptions

We have started to explore the open problems in metric learning (see 3.4) in a preliminary application. The goal of this pilot study was to identify features in visual representations of chemical molecules that influence students' perceptual similarity judgments. Figure 4 shows a low-dimensional embedding of Lewis diagrams derived from comparative judgments of the form "Is Diagram A more similar to Diagram B or C?" In this preliminary experiment, we used our open-source software system <http://nextml.org> to collect more than 6,000 comparative judgments from a class of undergraduate chemistry students at the University

Figure 4. Perceptual embedding machine-learned from human judgments. Clusters show perceptual similarities agree with known categories of molecules.

of Wisconsin–Madison (UW–Madison). We applied non-metric multidimensional scaling methods to determine the embedding depicted below. We have highlighted clusters in the embedding that correspond to specific chemical groups (which shows that perceptual similarities agree with the groups). Distances in this embedding reflect perceptual dissimilarity. We then used machine learning (regression) methods to identify which features (e.g., numbers of atoms, bounds, types of atoms, angles of bounds, etc.) are most predictive of the perceptual similarities. We compared the results to the “educated guesses” that instructional designers make about students’ perceptions based on the psychology literature. Remarkably, most of the key features discovered using these techniques agreed well with the “educated guesses” about which factors were hypothesized to be important in student perception. Moreover, the machine learning approach revealed additional key features that were surprising yet highly plausible. For example, students perceive molecules with sp^2 hybridization as a cluster separate from alkanes, even though alkanes have sp^3 hybridization. This finding may reflect that students in this experiment were relative novices in chemistry. The fact that the learned embedding is highly correlated with features believed to influence visual perception of similarity is a novel approach that lends support to the use of such embedding methods.

4.3 Machine Teaching to Reverse-Engineer Optimal Example Sets

Co-PI Zhu’s preliminary work provides evidence that machine teaching “works” for humans (Patil, Zhu, Kopec, & Love, 2014): We studied a human categorization task, where participants learn to classify line segments as short vs. long in a one-dimensional stimulus space. We formulated a machine teaching task where cognitive model A was a limited capacity retrieval model similar to a kernel density classifier. The teaching loss function encodes the desire for the teacher to minimize the student’s expected test error. Machine teaching identified an interesting optimal training set: The negative training items are tightly clumped together, so are the positive training items, and these items are symmetric but far away from the decision boundary, as illustrated in Figure 5. Human participants indeed generalized better from this optimal training set computed by machine teaching, compared to a control group who received *iid* uniformly sampled training sets. Both groups are tested on the same test set consisting of a dense grid over the feature space. The group that received machine-teaching training set had a significantly higher average test-set accuracy compared to the control group.

Figure 5. Optimal training set identified in Patil and colleagues (2014).

Our team is pilot-testing an expansion of the machine teaching method to the targeted perceptual learning tasks. To this end, we developed an algorithm that generates a training and test set based on the frequency with which molecules occur in the target curriculum corpus (i.e., undergraduate chemistry curricula) and based on the similarity between two given visual representations of molecules. We are collecting data via Amazon Mechanical Turk, where study participants given perceptual tasks that ask whether two visual representations show the same molecule. In the experiment, participants are presented with the perceptual task without feedback (pretest phase), then with correctness feedback (learning phase), and then again without feedback (posttest phase). The test sets and training sets do not contain the same molecules because we are interested in learning of transferable perceptual skills; that is, learning of visual features that transfer across different molecules.

5 Research Plan: Advancing Understanding of Learning in Technology-rich Environments

Our goal is to develop adaptive supports for perceptual fluency that can be integrated in educational technologies. To address this goal, we need to answer the following four questions, which correspond to the four steps in which we will carry out our research.

1. Which visual features do students and experts attend to when seeing visual representations?
2. What is an appropriate cognitive model that captures students’ perceptual learning processes?
3. Which selection and sequence of visual representations is *optimal* to enhance students’ perceptual fluency in an effective and efficient way?
4. Does the integration of adaptive perceptual support in an existing educational technology enhance students’ learning of the domain knowledge?

Answering these research questions will advance understanding of how people learn in technology-rich environments. Each phase of the research plan below addresses the generalizability and transferability of our findings in educational psychology, cognitive science, machine learning, and STEM teaching and learning. We focus on undergraduate chemistry because this domain uses visual representations in a similar way as many other STEM domains (Ainsworth, 2008; Gilbert, 2008). Therefore, we anticipate our research generalizes to other STEM domains.

5.1 Phase 1: Metric Learning to Determine Student and Expert Perceptions

A first step in developing traditional cognitive models of explicit knowledge is to create a model of the target domain knowledge (i.e., what knowledge do experts use when solving domain-relevant problems, and how do novices think about these problems). When creating a cognitive model of perceptual fluency, this first step corresponds to investigating which visual features chemistry experts pay attention to, and how these perceptions differ from the visual features that novice students attend to. To this end, we will develop a methodology to describe the visual features a given visual representations contains. Next, we will use metric learning to establish which features drive student and expert perceptions.

5.1.1 Develop Feature Dimension Description (Year 1)

Any visual representation can be described in terms of its visual features. At a technical level, we can describe each feature as a vector. For example, for the Lewis structure in Figure 1-a, relevant visual features may be the number of dots (i.e., unbonded electrons), the number of dashes (i.e., bonds), the number of letters (i.e., atoms), etc. We can thus imagine a set of vectors that specify whether the given visual representation contains each of these features.

Our first step in addressing Research Question 1 is to develop a methodology that allows us to describe any visual representation as a feature vector. Feature vectors describe visual representations computationally and yield a mapping of visual features among representations that students are expected to learn. At the same time, feature vectors can be used to assess the difficulty of translation tasks.

5.1.2 Experiment 1: Metric Learning to Compare Expert and Novice Perceptions (Year 1)

The second step in addressing Research Question 1 is to compare how novices and experts perceive visual representations. To this end, we will conduct an experiment in which novice chemistry undergraduate students and chemistry experts will be presented with perceptual translation tasks. Given one visual representation (e.g., a Lewis structure of methane), students will be asked which of two other visual representations (e.g., an EPM of ethane or an EPM of tetrachloride) is most similar to the Lewis structure. In analyzing data from this experiment, we will use the feature dimension description developed in the previous step. This approach will allow us to determine (1) which visual features experts pay attention to when translating between visual representations, (2) which features novices pay attention to, and (3) how novices and experts differ in this respect.

Novices will be $N = 100$ undergraduate chemistry students taking introductory chemistry courses at UW–Madison and at the Madison Area Technical College (MATC), a local 2-year college. The experiment will be conducted at the beginning of the semester to ensure students have low prior exposure to chemistry representations. Students will receive course credit for participating. As for experts, given that Chem Tutor is designed for general chemistry courses, we will recruit $N = 50$ professors and advanced graduate students in the field of general chemistry. We will recruit from UW–Madison’s Chemistry Department, and at the annual chemistry education conference and the annual meeting of the Chemistry Society. To make efficient use of chemistry experts’ time, we will draw on co-PI Nowak’s research on prioritizing comparison items that are most likely to yield the most information on the subject’s perceptions.

5.1.3 Phase 1: Summary of Contributions

Experiment 1 will make contributions to research on perceptual learning. We will use the data from Experiment 1 to identify those visual features that experts pay attention to whereas novices do not: These visual features are the ones that are most important for students to learn to attend to. Hence, the perceptual support will focus on these visual features. Our approach of evaluating feature vector descriptions with machine learning methods will serve to evaluate the common “educated guesses” approach while offering more formal pathways for instructional designers to create perceptual learning tasks.

Experiment 1 will contribute to the field of machine learning by enabling a new mathematical analysis to quantify the accuracy of perceptual embeddings learned from comparative judgments. Specifically, we will derive bounds on accuracy of embeddings learned from small numbers of comparative judgments by adapting recently developed large-sample analysis methods (Arias-Castro, 2015). This approach will provide new algorithms for generating embeddings that are provably accurate. We will investigate new methods for embedding based on spectral methods inspired by spectral ranking algorithms (Negahban et al., 2012). Experiment 1 will yield an empirical validation with perceptual data from novices and experts, as well as new machine learning methods to assess how visual features predict or encode perceptual similarity judgments. Specifically, we will explore the application of group Lasso algorithms for automatically selecting the most perceptually salient features (Yuan & Lin, 2006). The data from Experiment 1 will be used to empirically evaluate the group lasso approach.

5.2 Phase 2: Machine Learning to Develop Cognitive Model (Year 1)

Next, we will address Research Question 2: What is an appropriate cognitive model that captures students’ perceptual learning processes?

5.2.1 Experiment 2: Perceptual Learning (Year 1)

The first step is to collect data from the target population while they solve perceptual tasks. In Experiment 2, undergraduate chemistry students at UW–Madison and at MATC will be presented with perceptual tasks that correspond with Kellman and colleagues’ perceptual supports. Specifically, students will be given one visual representation (e.g., a Lewis structure of methane) and a second representation (e.g., an EPM of ethane). Their task is to judge whether the two visual representations show the same molecule.

The experiment involves three steps. First, in the pretest, students’ prior perceptual fluency will be assessed based on their performance on perceptual tasks. During the pretest, students will not receive feedback. Second, during the learning step, students will work on perceptual tasks while receiving correctness feedback on their response (i.e., whether their response was correct or incorrect). Third, during the post-test, students’ learning outcomes will be assessed based on their performance on perceptual tasks without feedback. In all three steps, the perceptual tasks will be presented in random sequence. In addition to prior perceptual fluency, we will assess students’ spatial abilities using the Vandenberg and Kuse mental rotations test (Peters et al., 1995), and students’ prior chemistry content knowledge, using a test developed in our lab (Rau et al., 2015). To recruit participants, students enrolled in introductory chemistry lectures will be asked to participate for course credit.

5.2.2 Develop Cognitive Model of Perceptual Learning (Year 2)

Using the data from Experiment 2, we will develop a cognitive model that describes students’ learning of perceptual fluency. We propose the following natural computational model as a cognitive model. Noting the similarity to multilingual machine translation, we conceptually describe each molecule by an additional “golden feature vector” g . The golden feature vector is a logical description of the molecule with features like the number of hydrogen atoms and serves as a common “language” for the other representations to translate to. For simplicity, we assume the translation from a representation (say w) to the golden feature vector is through linear operator A_w : $g = A_w w$. The parameters of the learning algorithm are the four operators $\theta = \{A_w, A_x, A_y, A_z\}$. Given two representations, say w and x , the learning algorithm makes an equivalence judgment y stochastically according to:

$$P(y = 1 | w, x; \theta) = \exp(-\|A_w w - A_x x\|_2^2)$$

During training, the learning algorithm estimates θ from a training set using regularized maximum likelihood. Note that golden feature vectors are a conceptual device; the student never actually observes them during training. This learning algorithm allows overfitting as we observed in human students: When the training set size is small (and not optimized), the estimated operators may focus on the wrong properties of the representations that happen to match the training data but do not generalize to novel examples.

We will compare several variants of the proposed cognitive model to determine whether students’ prior chemistry knowledge and their spatial abilities determine how they learn perceptual fluency. We will emphasize students’ learning of the visual features that we identified as important learning goals in Phase 1. To this end, we will introduce regularization methods or constraints reflecting prior knowledge into the

optimization used to fit an embedding to comparative judgments. We have developed a similar approach for the special case of ranking (Jamieson & Nowak, 2011) and we will extend this approach to the more challenging embedding problem using data from Experiment 2.

5.2.3 Develop Feature Feedback for Perceptual Tasks (Year 2)

Using the cognitive model developed in the previous step, we are in a position to incorporate more fine-grained feedback on students' performance on perceptual tasks during the learning phase. Specifically, the cognitive model will allow us to determine which visual feature a student failed to attend to when he/she provided a wrong answer. We will use Chem Tutor's color highlighting functions to draw students' attention to these visual features and pilot-test implementation of this feedback function in the lab.

5.2.4 Phase 2: Summary of Contributions

The research activities in Phase 2 will make an important contribution to the field of perceptual learning because it will provide a means to model latent skills involved in perceptual learning and a cognitive model of students' acquisition of perceptual fluency. This cognitive model will enable perceptual supports to provide more informative feedback for students' learning, as well as to adaptively sequence perceptual learning problems. Given that cognitive models have thus far been established for verbally accessible forms of knowledge, this research also makes an important contribution to the field of cognitive science.

Phase 2 research activities will also make novel contributions to the field of machine learning by providing new theory and methods for optimizing the selection of comparative judgments to minimize the burden on human subjects. This contribution is important because human subjects are often a scarce resource—for example when surveying chemistry professors, military personnel, disabled populations. The planned research will expand prior work by co-PI Nowak (Jamieson & Nowak, 2011) and the crowd kernel method (Tamuz et al., 2011). Experiment 2 serves as an empirical validation of these algorithms.

5.3 Phase 3: Machine Teaching to Determine Optimal Sequences of Perceptual Tasks (Year 2)

Next, we will address Research Question 3: Which selection and sequence of visual representations is *optimal* to enhance students' perceptual fluency in an effective and efficient way?

5.3.1 Machine Teaching (Year 2)

The first step is to apply co-PI Zhu's machine teaching approach. Using the learning algorithm developed in Phase 2, we will identify the optimal training set for this learning algorithm. The training-set space consists of training sets with varying number of training triplets that correspond to the perceptual learning tasks. The teaching risk function is the test set error, and the teaching effort function is the cardinality. The machine teaching task is well-defined but involves difficult combinatorial search. However, we may be able to relax the search space to allow continuous numbers of training triplets. We then solve the continuous version of the machine teaching problem and eventually round the optimal training set back to nonnegative integer counts of training items. (Mei & Zhu, 2015) successfully employed this technique when finding the optimal Bag-of-Words training corpus to teach latent Dirichlet allocation.

5.3.2 Experiment 3: Evaluating the Optimal Sequence (Year 2)

The second step in addressing Research Question 3 is to test whether the optimal sequences we developed using machine teaching lead to better learning outcomes. To this end, Experiment 3 will compare several versions of optimal sequences and a random sequence of perceptual tasks. The experiment will be carried out in the context of Chem Tutor and will hence include the new feature feedback functionality developed in Experiment 2. We will only use the perceptual tasks in Chem Tutor (i.e., not the other modules that focus on conceptual representation skills). As in Experiment 2, we will recruit undergraduate chemistry students through the UW–Madison Chemistry Department and from the MATC.

5.3.3 Experiment 4: Adaptive Perceptual Support (Year 3)

Building on the previous research activities, we will investigate Research Question 4: Does the integration of adaptive perceptual support in an existing educational technology enhance students' learning of the domain knowledge? To this end, we will integrate the best cognitive model and the optimal example sequence into Chem Tutor. Experiment 4 will involve three steps: a pretest, learning, and a posttest. During the learning step, chemistry students from UW–Madison and MATC will be randomly assigned to the new version of perceptual support that incorporates the new adaptive capabilities with the optimal exam-

ple sequence, or to a version of perceptual support with a random sequence of examples. Experiment 4 will be carried out within the full version of Chem Tutor with the existing conceptual supports for representation skills. We will assess students' chemistry knowledge and representation skills in the pretest and posttest phases. We will also assess spatial ability in the pretest phase.

We will test the hypothesis that students using the adaptive version of perceptual support will outperform students using the random version on measures of chemistry knowledge and representation skills. We will further test the hypothesis that students with low spatial ability may particularly benefit from adaptive perceptual support by testing for aptitude-treatment interaction effects among experimental condition and spatial ability. Finally, we will investigate whether women may particularly benefit from adaptive perceptual support by testing for interaction effects among experimental condition and gender to help facilitate tailoring of learning opportunities to this group of students.

5.4 Phase 3: Summary of Contributions

Phase 3 research activities will contribute to the field of perceptual learning by developing and evaluating a new version of perceptual support with adaptive capabilities based on a cognitive model of latent skills involved in perceptual learning. This research also expands prior research on machine learning by offering new methods for incorporating knowledge of known similarities (e.g., based on features known to influence perception or known characteristics of the human subjects involved). Using these methods to develop feature feedback in perceptual tasks (Year 2) and optimal sequences of perceptual tasks (Year 3) will provide an evaluation of their usefulness in practice. In sum, this project illustrates the merit of research at the intersection of educational psychology, cognitive science, and machine learning.

6 Broader Impacts of the Proposed Work

The *intellectual merit* of our project lies in combining educational psychology, cognitive science, and machine learning theory and research to transform cognitive modeling—which has well-documented advantages for supporting explicit, verbally mediated forms of learning. We will expand cognitive modeling to implicit forms of student learning, which will allow us to transform the adaptive capabilities of educational technologies for representation skills to support perceptual fluency. A representation skill overlooked by educational psychology research, perceptual fluency is a critical aspect of domain expertise. Our project will contribute a next-generation methodology that produces more efficient algorithms to model perceptual judgments. The *broader impacts* of our research result from the pervasiveness of representations in chemistry and other STEM learning. More effective and efficient support of representation skills will likely improve STEM instruction, an important driver of the U.S. economy. Further, by establishing ways to adapt to student characteristics (e.g., spatial ability, gender), we may better support students who tend to struggle in STEM, which may increase the fairness of STEM instruction. Finally, by integrating our research into educational technologies, which are easy to disseminate and play an increasingly important role in education, this project will likely benefit a large number of students.

7 Dissemination

We anticipate the new Chem Tutor, which will include adaptive supports for conceptual and perceptual representation skills, will significantly enhance students' learning of representation skills and of chemistry knowledge. In disseminating our research, we pursue three goals to achieve the interconnected thrusts that NSF supports, especially promoting use and transferability of Chem Tutor and our findings.

The first goal is to *promote chemistry learning among diverse student populations*. We will meet this goal by disseminating Chem Tutor. Chemistry instructors often have difficulty finding interactive representations and integrating them into courses (Williamson, 2011). We will create a website for instructors that details how to use Chem Tutor in undergraduate courses. In disseminating this website, we will reach out to undergraduate populations that include students at 2-year colleges who often strongly rely on distance education (Behrend, Wiebe, London, & Johnson, 2011). We will collaborate with instructors from Madison Area Technical College, a local 2-year college, as well as instructors from the Department of Chemistry at UW–Madison to promote Chem Tutor (see our letters of support). To further broaden adoption of Chem Tutor, we will inform instructors from 2- and 4-year colleges by sharing information through the Midwestern Association of Chemistry Teachers in Liberal Arts Colleges and the Two-Year

College Consortium. In doing so, we will draw on the support of the advisory board, which includes instructors at 2- and 4-year colleges (see support letters). Further, we will develop a workshop for the Biennial Conference on Chemical Education, which tailors content to educators at 2-year and 4-year colleges. The workshop will be designed to establish long-lasting collaborations with instructors in the STEM disciplines, which will further this research beyond the 3-year duration. A second way we will promote chemistry learning is by disseminating our findings to the chemistry education community. To this end, we will publish in the *Journal of Chemical Education* and present at conferences attended by practitioners (e.g., American Educational Research Association and the Biennial Conference on Chemical Education).

The second goal is to promote *adaptive perceptual support in a broad range of STEM domains*. We will target interdisciplinary conferences and journals, including the International Conference on Artificial Intelligence in Education, the International Conference on Intelligent Tutoring systems, the *Journal of Educational Psychology*, and the *Journal of Learning Sciences*. We will organize a workshop on adaptive educational technologies at the International Conference of the Learning Sciences in 2018; its papers will be included in a journal special issue. In disseminating this research, we seek to stimulate research on adaptive connection-making support in educational technologies, which will improve STEM education.

The third goal is to *disseminate our methodological contributions to the machine learning community*. We will present our research at the Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems, the International Conference on Machine Learning, the International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing, the Association for the Advancement of Artificial Intelligence (AAAI), the International Joint Conference on Artificial Intelligence, and the Annual Meeting of the Cognitive Science Society. We will submit a workshop proposal to the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) Workshop on Statistical Signal Processing.

8 Personnel

The project team combines expertise in educational psychology, adaptive educational technologies, machine learning, engineering, computer science, and chemistry education. The team has the expertise and resources to ensure that Chem Tutor aligns with undergraduate chemistry goals and meets the needs of undergraduate students and their instructors and campuses.

PI Dr. Martina Rau is an assistant professor in the Department of Educational Psychology at UW–Madison. She developed Chem Tutor and Fractions Tutor, an ITS that combines conceptual and perceptual support for representation skills, available for free (<https://fractions.cs.cmu.edu/>). Dr. Rau has extensive experience in conducting controlled classroom experiments with ITSs, in using user-centered design and multi-methods research. Dr. Rau’s work on Fractions Tutor received an honorable mention at the International Conference on Computer and Human Interactions (Rau, Aleven, Rummel, & Rohrbach, 2013). Her work on sense-making abilities and perceptual fluency won the best paper award at the International Conference on Educational Data Mining (Rau, Scheines et al., 2013). She has published in international journals such as the *Journal of Learning and Instruction* and the *Journal of Educational Psychology*.

Co-PI Dr. Xiaojin Zhu is an associate professor in the Department of Computer Sciences at UW–Madison. He employs statistical machine learning theory to study and enhance human learning. Dr. Zhu has extensive experience collaborating with psychologists at UW–Madison and internationally. He received the NSF CAREER Award in 2010 and several best paper awards. His work on machine teaching, one of the pillars of the proposed project, was awarded the AAAI / Computing Community Consortium “Blue Sky Ideas” Track Prize in 2015.

Co-PI Dr. Robert Nowak is the McFarland-Bascom Professor in Engineering at UW–Madison, where his research focuses on signal processing, machine learning, optimization, and statistics. Dr. Nowak is a professor in the Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering, and affiliated with the departments of Computer Sciences and Biomedical Engineering. He is a fellow of the IEEE and the Wisconsin Institute for Discovery, a member of the Wisconsin Optimization Research Consortium, and organizer of an interdisciplinary seminar on data science. Dr. Nowak has received numerous research awards, including the 2014 IEEE W. R. G. Baker Award for most outstanding paper.

The **advisory board** complements the PI's expertise. **Dr. Philip Kellman**, professor in the Psychology Department at the University of California, Los Angeles, spearheaded the development of perceptual supports in educational technologies. He will provide feedback on assessments of perceptual fluency and on the design of perceptual tasks. Two board members will assist the research team in recruiting participants for the experiments and in disseminating the new version of Chem Tutor. **Dr. John Moore**, professor in the UW–Madison's Department of Chemistry, is the director of the Institute for Chemical Education and was the editor of the *Journal of Chemical Education*. **Dr. Christen Smith**, instructor at Madison Area Technical College, has extensive experience teaching chemistry with representations. **Dr. Richard Baraniuk** is the Victor E. Cameron Professor of Electrical and Computer Engineering at Rice University, Houston, Texas, where he is developing advanced machine learning algorithms and a software platform for a personalized learning system. He will provide feedback on the machine learning methods developed and applied in this project. **Dr. Michael Mozer** is professor in Department of Computer Science and Institute of Cognitive Science at University of Colorado, Boulder, where he studies computational models of human cognition to improve how people learn, remember, and make decisions. He will provide feedback on designing cognitive models and developing educational technologies.

9 Project Management

The PI, Dr. Rau, will provide scientific direction and guidance to her project team and will oversee all aspects of the project, including development of the new version of Chem Tutor's perceptual fluency support; pilot studies; the design, execution, and analysis related to the experiments; and relations with participating instructors. Co-PI, Dr. Zhu and Dr. Nowak, will oversee the analysis of the experiments that involve metric learning, machine learning, and machine teaching. Dr. Rau will serve as the primary academic advisor to a Ph.D. student enrolled in the Department of Educational Psychology. Co-PI Nowak will serve as the primary advisor to a Ph.D. student recruited from the Department of Electrical and Computer Engineering in year 1, Co-PI Zhu will serve as the primary advisor to a Ph.D. student in the Department of Computer Sciences in years 2 and 3. All three Co-PIs will jointly advise all Ph.D. students. Undergraduate students will be involved in these activities as part of a research-study program for which they earn course credit at UW–Madison.

The research team will organize full-day virtual advisory board meetings twice a year. Meetings will take place prior to experiments for members of the board to provide feedback on the experimental design, assessment, and analysis plans. In meetings held after the experiments, board members will review plans for the iterative improvement based on results, supplementary data analysis, and dissemination. Experiment 4 will serve as a final evaluation of the new version of Chem Tutor, which will be disseminated after that experiment. A detailed timeline is below.

Time	Development	Empirical work
Year 1: 2016-17		
Fall '16	Feature description of visual representations	Experiment 1: Expert-novice comparison
Spring '17	Validate feature description using data from Experiment 1	Experiment 2: Perceptual learning
Summer '17	Analyze data Experiment 2 data; develop cognitive model	Write paper on Experiment 1
Year 2: 2017-18		
Fall '17	Develop feature feedback; develop optimal example sets using machine teaching	Write paper on Experiment 2; pilot-test feature feedback
Spring '18		Experiment 3: Optimal sequences
Summer '18	Analyze data from Experiment 3; revise cognitive model based on Experiment 3 results	
Year 3: 2018-19		
Fall '18	Implement optimal sequences and cognitive model into Chem Tutor to create adaptive version	Write paper on Experiment 3; pilot run of adaptive version Chem Tutor
Spring '19	Analyze data from Experiment 4	Experiment 4: Evaluation
Summer '19	Make final modifications to Chem Tutor	Write, disseminate Experiment 4 paper